

1 **Target Gas Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry Analysis of Honey**
2 **Samples for Determining Plastic-Related Chemicals: Green Sample**
3 **Treatment Optimization and Method Validation**

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5 Adrián Fuente-Ballesteros, Ana M. Ares, José Bernal, Silvia Valverde*

6 Analytical Chemistry Group (TESEA), I. U. CINQUIMA, Faculty of Sciences, University of
7 Valladolid, 47011, Valladolid, Spain.

8 ***Corresponding author:** Tel# 34-983184249; silvia.valverde@uva.es

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23 **Abstract**

24 A novel analytical methodology has been optimized and developed for the comprehensive
25 identification and quantification of six phthalates, one adipate, and two ethers within honey
26 samples using gas chromatography-mass spectrometry (GC-MS). The sample preparation
27 process involved a sustainable dual solvent extraction technique utilizing ethyl acetate,
28 followed by a subsequent clean-up step. Simultaneously, chromatographic analysis,
29 completed within a timeframe of less than 21 minutes, was executed using a DB-5MS column
30 operating under programmed temperature conditions. The method underwent rigorous
31 validation encompassing multiple parameters such as selectivity, limits of detection (0.03-
32 3.10 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), and quantification (0.1-10.3 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$), linearity, matrix effect (within $\pm 20\%$),
33 accuracy (recoveries from 70% to 120%), and precision (relative standard deviation below
34 10% in all cases). Notably, all examined honey samples, sourced from diverse botanical
35 origins (n = 30), exhibited the presence of at least one plasticizer, with diethyl phthalate,
36 benzyl butyl phthalate, and bis(2-ethylhexyl) adipate being the most prevalent. Nevertheless,
37 all concentrations were below the specific migration limits established by the European
38 Commission and thorough a risk assessment, they were considered safe for human
39 consumption.

40 **Keywords:** food analysis; food safety; gas chromatography-mass spectrometry; method
41 validation; plasticizers; honey; sample treatment.

42 **1. Introduction**

43 Based on the floral origin, honey is classified as either mono- or multifloral, making it a
44 natural food. The primary components of it are sugars, with monosaccharides making up
45 approximately 75% of the total sugar content, disaccharides from 10% to 15% of the total,
46 and other carbohydrates representing 0.1% of the total. Additionally, it contains enzymes,
47 amino acids, organic acids, carotenoids, vitamins, minerals, and 7.9% of aromatic substances
48 that have a variety of biological effects and function as natural antioxidants (Taş-Küçükaydın
49 et al., 2023). Honey, a universally sweet food, is consumed worldwide. Due to its widespread
50 popularity, it necessitates standards and regulations ensuring its identity and quality. These
51 measures are crucial for ensuring the safe consumption of honey by consumers and enabling
52 its unrestricted circulation in both domestic and international markets (FAO, 2022).
53 Numerous studies have focused on assessing the presence of contaminants like metals
54 (Mititelu et al., 2023; Ploegaerts et al., 2023), pesticides (Brugnerotto et al., 2023; Fuente-
55 Ballesteros, Brugnerotto, et al., 2023; Fuente-Ballesteros, Nozal, et al., 2023), and antibiotics
56 (Bonerba et al., 2021; Shendy et al., 2016; Yang et al., 2022) in honey to ensure its safety.
57 However, research examining the occurrence of plasticizers in honey remains relatively
58 limited (Cao et al., 2015; Di Fiore et al., 2023; Kartalovic et al., 2021; Koo et al., 2017; Lo
59 Turco et al., 2016; Massous et al., 2023; Notardonato et al., 2020b, 2020a; Peñalver et al.,
60 2021; von Eyken et al., 2020; Zhou et al., 2014). Plasticizers are employed to augment the
61 elasticity, flexibility, color, resistance, and longevity of diverse plastic polymers employed in
62 food packaging applications. These substances lack chemical bonds with the polymer chains
63 present in the plastics, thereby enabling the potential migration from the packaging materials
64 into the food substances they are in contact with, gradually over time (Peñalver et al., 2021).
65 A plethora of plasticizers, among them phthalates (PAEs), adipates, and related chemical
66 compounds like ethers, are presently employed in food packaging (Cohen et al., 2023; Lu et al.,

67 2023; Özgür et al., 2023; Rahman & Brazel, 2004). These plasticizers have been detected in
68 various food matrices, such as rice, cereals, milk, sweets, fruits, vegetables, eggs, meat, fish,
69 or oil (Blanco-Zubiaguirre et al., 2021; Cao et al., 2014; Cirillo & Amodio Cocchieri, 2013; Dugo et al.,
70 2011; Zhang et al., 2022) and honey samples (see Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**).
71 According to that, the European Commission defined specific migration limits (SMLs) on
72 plastic materials and articles intended to come into contact with food (Official Journal of the
73 European Union, 2011, 2023).

74

75 PAEs, notably dimethyl phthalate (DMP), diethyl phthalate (DEP), dibutyl phthalate (DBP),
76 benzyl butyl phthalate (BBP), bis(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate (DEHP) and di-n-octyl phthalate
77 (DNOP) have a prominent role within the polymer industry. These PAEs find extensive use in
78 various food-packaging materials, including paper, cardboard, plastics, metal closures of glass
79 jars, cans, tetra bricks, and in food processing (Dobaradaran et al., 2020). Moreover, they are
80 present in gloves used for handling food (Lo Turco et al., 2016). Despite their role in
81 improving plastic properties, they pose detrimental effects on human health. These
82 compounds are linked to fertility issues and adverse impacts on newborn development
83 (Songue Same et al., 2023). Moreover, PAEs act as endocrine disruptors and carcinogens
84 (Giuliani et al., 2020). For example, DBP have been associated with toxicity affecting neural,
85 reproductive, and developmental systems (Moreira et al., 2013).

86

87 Bis(2-ethylhexyl)adipate (DEHA), a widely used plasticizer, is found in food contact
88 materials such as polyvinyl chloride (PVC) food wrapping film and polyethylene
89 terephthalate (PET) bottles (Cao et al., 2014; Lo Turco et al., 2016; Yamini et al., 2009).
90 Studies propose that wrapping food in PVC films could be the origin of elevated DEHA
91 levels observed in various food types across Canada (Cao et al., 2015), thus food items

92 packaged within these films stand as the primary source of human exposure to this plasticizer
93 (Goulas et al., 2007).

94

95 Furthermore, the food packaging materials may contain polychlorinated biphenyl ethers,
96 dichlorodiphenyl, dichloroethylene, phenanthrene, brominated flame retardants, and heavy
97 metals (Sewwandi et al., 2023). During the plastic production process, brominated flame
98 retardants serve as essential safety components. Among these, halodiphenyl ethers (HDEs),
99 such as 4-bromodiphenyl ether (4-BDE) and 4-chlorodiphenyl ether (4-CDE) are a commonly
100 utilized type, found in various plastic products like electronic thermoplastics and textiles
101 (Alabi et al., 2019). HDEs make up approximately 5-30% by weight of plastic products, and
102 their lack of chemical bonding to the polymer allows them to potentially leach out, leading to
103 environmental contamination (Office for Official Publications of the European Communities,
104 2001). HDEs act as hormone disruptors, affecting the activity of thyroid hormones and
105 estrogen, thereby impacting the development of both the nervous and reproductive systems
106 (Meeker et al., 2009; Rudel et al., 2003). Elevated levels of these toxins have been observed
107 in the serum, breast milk, and adipose tissue of exposed individuals (Frederiksen et al., 2009).

108

109 Gas chromatography (GC) and liquid chromatography (LC) have been the two most widely
110 utilized techniques for determining chemical compounds that migrate from plastic into food.
111 Regarding LC, a range of detectors has been coupled to the equipment, primarily relying on
112 fluorescence (Han et al., 2019), ultraviolet (Paseiro-Cerrato et al., 2019a, 2019b; Xiao et al.,
113 2019), time of flight-mass spectrometry (TOF-MS) (Bauer et al., 2019; Lian et al., 2020), and
114 tandem mass spectrometry (MS/MS) (Paseiro-Cerrato et al., 2019a, 2019b). When it comes to
115 GC, MS has been identified as the most suitable detection method (Notardonato et al., 2019;
116 Qian et al., 2018; Žnideršič et al., 2019). Sample preparation methods such as solid-phase

117 extraction (SPE) and solvent extraction (SE) have been employed. Regarding sample
118 preparation methods, microextraction techniques such as dispersive liquid-liquid
119 microextraction (DLLME) (Koo et al., 2017) have been utilized to ascertain organic toxic
120 compounds released into food. Additionally, the literature references ultrasound-assisted
121 emulsification microextraction (USAEME) with ionic liquids (ILs) (Cacho et al., 2017) and
122 magnetic solid-phase extraction (MSPE) utilizing nanocomposite monolithic extractant
123 materials (Gorji et al., 2019). However, the most commonly employed techniques for
124 studying plasticizers in honey rely on traditional methods employing SPE or SE (see
125 Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**).

126

127 Out of the total papers available in the databases focusing on the analysis of PAEs, adipates,
128 or ethers in honey samples (n = 12), 92% examined PAEs and 34% investigated adipates.
129 However, none of these studies considered the HDEs (see Supplementary Material, **Table**
130 **1S**). Authors started with the premise that plasticizers represent pervasive environmental
131 contaminants, with many exhibiting the potential to migrate from plastic materials into food
132 upon contact. This migration process can take place during various stages including food
133 processing, packaging, storage, and transportation. While multiple sources of exposure to
134 plasticizers exist, contaminated food and beverages stand as the primary route for human
135 exposure.

136

137 Specifically, honey is recognized as a high-value-added product that might potentially be
138 contaminated by this type of plastic-related chemicals. The contamination may stem from via
139 two routes: i) Migration from packaging materials into the honey during storage. The acidic
140 nature of honey and its high moisture content can impact the distribution of plastic additives
141 between the bottle and the honey, potentially contributing to the leaching of toxic compounds

142 (Peñalver et al., 2021); ii) Environmental contamination might occur through the release of
143 plasticizers into the air, soil, or water, and bees could collect these compounds during the
144 gathering of nectar and pollen, resulting in the presence of plasticizers in honey. Thus,
145 evaluating the presence of plasticizers in honey is paramount to safeguarding consumer
146 health, ensuring food quality, and complying with established food regulations and standards.
147 According to that, in this paper it has been developed and validated an analytical methodology
148 based on a double SE couple with GC-MS to investigate six PAEs, one adipate, and two
149 HDEs in honey samples sourced from diverse botanical and geographical origins. To the best
150 of our knowledge, this study stands as the pioneering to scrutinize this simultaneous group of
151 analytes utilizing an analytical methodology in agreement with the green analytical chemistry
152 principles (GAC) (Gałuszka et al., 2013).

153

154 **2. Materials and methods**

155 **2.1. Reagents and materials**

156 PAEs, adipate, and HDEs standards (BBP, DBP, dibutyl phthalate-3,4,5,6-d₄ (DBP-d₄),
157 DEHP, DEP, DMP, DNOP, DEHA, 4-BDE and 4-CDE; see structures in Supplementary
158 Material, **Table 2S**), all of analytical-grade and with purity greater than 98%, were purchased
159 from Sigma-Aldrich Chemie Gbmh (Steinheim, Germany). An isotope labeled standard
160 (DBP-d₄) was chosen as internal standard (IS), since it has the same physical and chemical
161 properties as the unlabeled analyte. Dichloromethane (LC grade) was supplied by Lab Scan
162 Ltd. (Dublin, Ireland), chloroform (LC grade) by Scharlab S. L. (Barcelona, Spain), acetone
163 (LC grade) by Carlo Erba Reagents-SA (Milan, Italy), nitric acid (Analytical-grade) by ITW
164 Reagents (Monza, Italy) and methyl tert-butyl ether by Sigma-Aldrich Chemie Gbmh
165 (Steinheim, Germany). The rest of solvents (ethyl acetate, cyclohexane, hexane, acetonitrile,
166 acetic acid, and ammonia) were of chromatographic grade and obtained from VWR Prolabo

167 Chemicals (Fontenay-sous-Bois, France). Ultrapure water was obtained using Millipore Milli-
168 RO plus and Milli-Q systems (Bedford, MA, USA). A vortex mechanical mixer from
169 Heidolph (Schwabach, Germany), a drying oven, and a vibromatic mechanical shaker, all
170 supplied by J.P. Selecta S.A. (Barcelona, Spain), a 5810 R refrigerated bench-top centrifuge
171 from Eppendorf (Hamburg, Germany), and PTFE syringe filters (17 mm, 0.22 μm ; Branchia,
172 Pais) were employed for sample treatment. Sep-Pak[®] Florisil (500 mg of sorbent; Waters,
173 Milford, MA) cartridge, and a 10-port Visiprep vacuum manifold (Supelco, Bellefonte, PA),
174 were used for the SPE extractions. In addition, NaCl, florisil and alumina were supplied by
175 Merck (Germany) and C₁₈ was provided by Supelco (Bellefonte, PA, USA). IBM SPSS
176 Statistics 27.0 software (SPSS Inc., Chicago, IL, USA) was used for heatmap and boxplot
177 graphs.

178

179 **2.2. Standards**

180 Standard stock ($\approx 1000\text{-}2000\text{ mg L}^{-1}$) and working solutions of the studied compounds (PAEs,
181 adipate, and HDEs) were prepared in acetone. Two separate stock solutions were prepared
182 according to commercially available standards. One mixture contained six PAEs (BBP, DBP,
183 DEHP, DEP, DMP and DNOP), and DEHA and the other was composed by the six PAEs
184 along with the two HDEs (4-BDE and 4-CDE). Honey samples, in which the absence of
185 plasticizers residues had been previously confirmed using GC-MS (blank samples) were
186 spiked with different amounts of the analytes before (BF samples) or after (AF samples)
187 sample treatment (see subsection 2.3). The spiking protocol was adapted from a previous
188 work (Fuente-Ballesteros, Brugnerotto, et al., 2023; see Supplementary Material, Table 3S).
189 The IS was always added at the same concentration (0.1 mg L^{-1}) to all samples. These
190 samples were used for validation (spiked samples (low, medium, and high) and calibration

191 curves), as well as sample treatment studies. Three replicates which were injected three times,
192 were prepared for all the studies. Each spiked sample was prepared with a blank sample
193 spiked with three different concentrations of the plasticizers within the linear range. These
194 were as follows: low-LOQ (see **Table 1**); medium-500 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$; high-1000 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$. The
195 standard stock solutions were stored in glass containers in darkness at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$, and working
196 and standard matrix solutions were stored in glass containers and kept in the dark at $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$.

197

198 **2.3. Sample procurement and treatment**

199 **2.3.1. Samples**

200 Honey samples ($n = 30$) were generously provided by beekeepers from various regions in
201 Spain, sourced from the Center for Agroenvironmental and Apicultural Investigation
202 (Marchamalo, Guadalajara, Spain), or acquired from local supermarkets in Valladolid, Spain;
203 Helsinki, Finland; and Tallin, Estonia. Selection criteria included diverse factors such as their
204 botanical origin, different shades, packaging, and overall composition. It is noteworthy that
205 the botanical sources of all samples were verified through melissopalynological analysis (see
206 Supplementary Material, **Table 4S**). The color of honey was assessed using a portable
207 photometer (HI96785 honey color, Hanna Instruments). Each sample underwent individual
208 homogenization through stirring with a glass rod and was subsequently stored in separate
209 tubes in darkness at $4\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ until analysis. To determine the plasticizer content, three replicates
210 (sub-samples) from each honey sample were injected in triplicate in the chromatographic
211 system.

212

213 2.3.2. Sample treatment

214 Briefly, 1.0 g of homogenized honey sample was weighed in a 10 mL screw-cap glass
215 centrifuge tube, after which 2 mL of ultrapure water was added, and the tube was shaken for 1
216 min in a vortex device. Next, 2 mL ethyl acetate was added to the tube and then shaken again
217 in a vibromatic device (10 min; 750 rpm) and centrifugated (4000 rpm) for 10 min. The
218 maximum volume of the supernatant was collected and kept in a vial while a second solvent
219 extraction was performed as previously described. Both supernatants were collected and
220 transferred to a screw-cap glass centrifuge tube containing 50 mg of Florisil. Then, the tube
221 was shaken in a vibromatic device (5 min; 750 rpm) and centrifuged (4000 rpm) for 5 min.
222 Two milliliters were evaporated to dryness using a gentle nitrogen steam. Finally, the dry
223 residue was reconstituted with 1 mL of an IS solution (0.1 mg L⁻¹), and it was passed through
224 a 0.22 µm PTFE filter prior GC-MS analysis. **Figure 1** summarizes the steps of the selected
225 sample treatment.

226

227 Additionally, since plasticizers are commonly present in the materials used in the laboratory,
228 their use was avoided to ensure good laboratory practices (Kartalovic et al., 2021; Lo Turco et
229 al., 2016; Massous et al., 2023; Peñalver et al., 2021). A cleaning procedure was implemented
230 to prevent cross-contamination caused by reagents, materials, and laboratory equipment.
231 Firstly, the glassware was soaked in ultrapure water, washed with 0.2 M nitric acid, and
232 sonicated for 20 minutes. Then, it was rinsed again with ultrapure water and subjected to the
233 same ultrasonic conditions. Subsequently, it was washed with acetone:methanol (1:1, v/v)
234 mixture, dried at 70 °C for at least 1 hour, and finally covered with aluminum foil until
235 analysis. A laminar flow cabinet was utilized, and no laboratory gloves were used during
236 sample weighing.

237

238 **2.4. GC-MS parameters**

239 An Agilent Technologies (Palo Alto, CA, USA) 7890A GC coupled to an Agilent Technologies
240 5975C MS equipped with an ALS 7693B autosampler and a MS ChemStation E 01.00.237
241 software (Agilent Technologies) was used. The GC-MS parameters, including the column
242 (Agilent DB-5MS; 30 m × 0.25 mm × 0.25 μm) were selected according to previous works (see
243 Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**), and under these conditions all compounds eluted in less
244 than 21 min (see **Figure 2**). Analyses were performed in selected ion monitoring mode (SIM),
245 with one target/quantification and two qualifier ions for each analyte (see **Table 1**). Detailed
246 conditions of the GC-MS parameters are described in **Table 2**.

247

248 **3. Results and discussion**

249 **3.1. Selection of GC-MS conditions**

250 In this study, different initial oven temperatures and ramping procedures were initially
251 examined to attain suitable retention time and satisfactory peak resolution. The initial column
252 oven temperature was set as follows: starting at 60 °C, increasing from 60 to 170 °C at a rate
253 of 40 °C min⁻¹, and then from 170 to 310 °C at a rate of 8 °C min⁻¹ (3 min hold). Despite this
254 setup, effective separation of the 9 compounds was not achieved due to the overlap between
255 the peaks of the two HDEs, 4-BDE and 4-CDE, owing to their closely aligned retention times.
256 Consequently, a decision was made to modify the chromatographic ramp conditions. A trial
257 was conducted starting from 60 °C (for 1 min) to 125 °C (for 3.6 min) at a rate of 25 °C min⁻¹,
258 followed by an increase to 310 °C (for 22.1 min) at a rate of 10 °C min⁻¹, with a final hold at
259 310 °C. Under these modified ramp conditions, the chromatogram resulted in a runtime of 25
260 min, incorporating 5 min for pre/post processing and conditioning. Moreover, the analytes

261 eluted in less than 21 minutes. Meticulous adjustments to other parameters were performed
262 using GC–MS solution software to enhance the separation of the targeted analytes. Once the
263 retention time of each analyte had been determined in full-scan mode, the subsequent step
264 involved optimizing the conditions for the SIM mode to ensure effective identification and a
265 high signal intensity for each target analyte. A full scan of the standard solution for each
266 plasticizer was conducted to display its mass spectrum and compare it with the NIST mass
267 spectra library. Molecular ions, highly abundant fragment ions, and characteristic ions with
268 selectivity to minimize cross-interferences were selected and fine-tuned to enable the
269 qualification and quantification of the analytes. Following the criteria set by these parameters,
270 we ultimately designated one specific ion for quantification purposes and two other ions for
271 qualitative assessment for each plasticizer (see **Table 1**).

272

273 **3.2. Optimization of the sample treatment**

274 We decided to begin the optimization of the sample treatment with thyme honey by
275 evaluating some of the procedures (SE, SPE and DLLME) that they have been already
276 proposed in the literature (see Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**). It should be specified that
277 1.0 g of samples (analyte free-blank, AF and BF) samples were employed in these preliminary
278 experiments and an intermediate spiked concentration of 0.25 mg L⁻¹ was used for recovery
279 studies.

280

281 We initially tested the suitability of DLLME by evaluating the performance of three different
282 extractant solvents (chloroform, acetone, and dichloromethane), as this extraction technique
283 had been employed in previous publications (Koo et al., 2017; Notardonato et al., 2020b,
284 2020a; Peñalver et al., 2021). Extractant solvents were rapidly injected into the disperser

285 solvent (acetonitrile) by means of a microsyringe, but no cloudy solution was formed so its
286 used was discarded. Next, the viability of SPE was then tested as it had been widely used in
287 food matrices (Carro et al., 2021; Ferrone et al., 2023; Salazar-Beltrán et al., 2017),
288 specifically in honey (Lo Turco et al., 2016). The obtained results were not good due to
289 clogging of the florisil cartridges, the presence of interfering peaks, and the recovery values
290 were only acceptable for two out of nine analytes (data not shown). We then decided to apply
291 SE-based methodologies that provided a good performance for determining the
292 plasticizers in honeys (see Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**). Different SE were performed
293 varying the extractant solvent (Dichloromethane: Acetone (1:1, v/v); ethyl acetate (EtOAc):
294 cyclohexane (1:1, v/v)), but unfortunately, we did not obtain acceptable results due to the co-
295 elution of some analytes, including DNOP, or possibly because of poor homogenization of the
296 honey in the extraction mixture. Next, we explored the possibility of using green solvents
297 such as methyl tert-butyl ether, but the recoveries were still inadequate (< 50%). Natural deep
298 eutectic solvents (NADES) were also examined. Multiple bicomponent mixtures (1:1, 1:2,
299 2:1; v/v) composed of thymol and lauric acid, 1,2-propanediol, camphor, and hexanedioic acid
300 were tested (ref). The results were unfavorable as several issues were encountered with these
301 extracting agents, such as solidification, failure to form two phases, or high viscosity. Hence,
302 their use was dismissed. In order to enhance both extraction efficacy and recovery values for
303 all analytes simultaneously, the method was modified from a single SE to a double SE using
304 solvents previously employed by other researchers. Different extracting solvents were
305 assessed, yielding a remarkable enhancement when utilizing the green solvent EtOAc (see
306 Supplementary Material, **Figure 1SA**). Thus, when we employed EtOAc as extractant solvent
307 it was the first time that acceptable recovery (**X-X%**) and matrix effect values (**< ±X%**) were
308 obtained for all analytes. Among all the tests performed, the best values in terms of recovery
309 percentages and matrix effect were obtained when using 1 g of sample, 2 mL of water, 2 mL

310 of extractant solvent, 10 min of shaking time, 10 min of centrifugation, and 2 mL of
311 supernatant. Consequently, it was decided to continue the optimization procedure with a
312 double SE by testing the influence of some crucial parameters: i) ionic strength; ii) shaking
313 device; and iii) pH control. First, the effect of ionic strength using a solution of NaCl 16% and
314 0.2 g of NaCl (Cao et al., 2015; Peñalver et al., 2021) was studied but no significant
315 improvement in terms of recovery was obtained (see Supplementary Material, **Figure 1SB**).
316 The same conclusion was reached by replacing vibromatic with ultrasound-assisted agitation,
317 which significantly worsened DENOP recovery by 53%. Subsequently, pH control was
318 implemented as it had been identified as a critical parameter by other researchers
319 (Notardonato et al., 2020a; Sewwandi et al., 2023). For instance, Notardonato et al. (2020b)
320 (Notardonato et al., 2020b) argued that pH selection is pivotal for the success of the procedure
321 and must be meticulously monitored and adjusted, given that PAEs exhibit better extraction at
322 an alkaline pH, yet they are only recoverable at pH 4. We conducted trials adjusting the pH
323 within the range of 4.0-5.0 using an acetic acid:ammonia mixture, but no significant
324 improvements were observed in the recovery values and matrix effect, consequently leading
325 to its exclusion (see Supplementary Material, **Figure 1SC**). Once previous conditions were
326 optimized, new alternatives were evaluated for reducing the matrix effect through a clean-up
327 step. Some sorbents were studied in different amounts and combinations to reduce the
328 interferences from the matrix (alumina, C₁₈, and florisil). For example, alumina can adsorb a
329 wide range of compounds, including, fatty acids, steroids, and other organic molecules,
330 thereby aiding in the purification of honey extracts; C₁₈ efficiently eliminates certain lipids,
331 and florisil removes lipids and polar compounds. As can be seen in **Figure 1SD** (see
332 Supplementary Material), the use of 50 mg of florisil provided quite good results for reducing
333 the matrix effect recoveries (from -X% to X%), without affecting the good recoveries of the
334 analytes (from X% to X%), so it was decided to incorporate this sorbent into the sample

335 treatment method. Ultimately, we attempted to shorten the sample preparation time by
336 reducing the vibromatic agitation from 10 to 5 minutes and replacing it with a 1-minute
337 vortex agitation for salt mixing, instead of the original 5-minute vibromatic agitation.
338 However, the results declined significantly, prompting us to maintain the initial conditions
339 (data not shown). Finally, 2 mL of both combined supernatants were transferred to a vial and
340 gently evaporated. For extract concentration, the suitability of using a stream of N₂ was tested
341 against the use of a rotary evaporator. The rotary evaporator, operating under vacuum
342 pressure at both 40 °C and room temperature, resulted in the breakdown and subsequent
343 disappearance of small ether molecules in the chromatogram; hence, we discarded its use.
344 When employing a gentle stream of nitrogen, no loss of analytes was observed during the
345 evaporation step. Once the sample treatment for thyme honey was fully optimized, and it was
346 checked that the recoveries (from 70% to 120%) and matrix effect (from X% to X%) were
347 good enough for all the compounds at the different concentration levels assayed (see **Table**
348 **3**), the suitability of the proposed sample treatment for two other botanical origins (heather
349 and rosemary) was evaluated. Results showed that it can be successfully employed to both
350 types of new honey, due to the good results obtained for the recovery (from X% to X%) and
351 matrix effect studies (from X% to X%) for all the plasticizers at the three concentration levels
352 studied (see **Table 3**).

353

354 To the best of our knowledge, this is the first time that a sample method has been developed
355 for a cocktail of plasticizers (6 PAEs, 1 adipate, and 2 HDEs) in honey samples from three
356 botanical origins. Notably, existing literature tends to address these compound groups
357 individually. The samples studied in literature do not pose the same challenges as beehive
358 products, notably honey - a complex apicultural product (Fuente-Ballesteros et al., 2024) -
359 which encompasses sugars, organic acids, polyphenols, amino acids, proteins, minerals, and

360 volatile compounds (Peñalver et al., 2021). The presence of such component diversity
361 significantly amplifies the difficulty in separating and individually identifying each
362 constituent. Additionally, these are some of the advantages compared to previous works in
363 which high volumes of solvents (Kartalovic et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2014), sample amount
364 (Di Fiore et al., 2023; Kartalovic et al., 2021; Lo Turco et al., 2016; Massous et al., 2023;
365 Notardonato et al., 2020b, 2020a; Zhou et al., 2014), solvent toxicity (Kartalovic et al., 2021;
366 Notardonato et al., 2020b, 2020a; Peñalver et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2014), or very long
367 sample preparation times (Kartalovic et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2014) were required.
368 Furthermore, the validation of the proposed method considered satisfactory recovery values
369 and matrix effects, marking a notable advancement from prior studies. The latter concern
370 holds significant importance when dealing with beehive products, given their intricate
371 compositions—an aspect frequently overlooked by numerous researchers (see Supplementary
372 Material, **Table 1S**).

373

374 **3.3 Greenness evaluation**

375 Analytical greenness calculator (AGREE), AGREEprep and complex green analytical
376 procedure index (GAPI) metrics were applied to rate the greenness of the developed method,
377 giving a similar final score. Considering all the metrics available in the literature, the three
378 ones were selected for being the most commonly used in the last years (see **Figures 3A, 3B**
379 and **3C**). All of them are commonly applied and free software is available along with detailed
380 description of their application (Pena-Pereira et al., 2020, 2022; Plotka-Wasyłka & Wojnowski,
381 2021; Shi et al., 2023; Wojnowski et al., 2022). In general, AGREE offers an overall assessment
382 of process sustainability, whereas AGREEprep focuses primarily on the sample preparation
383 step considering factors like the quantity and type of solvents used, extraction efficiency, and
384 waste generation. Complex GAPI is a more intricate metric, incorporating a broader array of

385 parameters, often more specific and stringent. Its purpose is to evaluate the eco-efficiency and
386 environmental impact of an analytical procedure in greater detail.

387

388 AGREE and AGREEprep metrics are based on 12 criteria, transformed into a 0-1 scale, where
389 the final score is determined by the collective contribution of all these criteria (see **Figures**
390 **3A** and **3B**). Offline measurements (parameter 3), eight or more steps in the analytical process
391 (parameter 4), and the use of energy expenditure by GC-MS (parameter 9) were negatively
392 weighted by the AGREE metric. A low degree of automation was also penalized (highlighted
393 in yellow; parameter 5). In contrast, the rest of the parameters in green color (sample
394 treatment activities, type of analysis, derivatization status, amount of waste, number of
395 analytes per hour, toxic reagents, and operator safety) aligned with the GAC principles.
396 Focusing on the AGREEprep, the ex-situ sample preparation placement and the high number
397 of sample preparation steps for double extraction with solvents were the parameters that had
398 the most negative influence on the final score. Hazardous solvents/reagents and operator
399 safety were underscored by both metrics as the most significant contributions to the green
400 values. As expected, the greenness scores calculated using both metrics were quite similar and
401 close to 1, indicating good compliance with the green principles. Both metrics are more
402 flexible and yield results that are easier to interpret compared to Complex GAPI.

403

404 Complex GAPI is an extensive and semi-quantitative GAC metric that can be utilized for
405 assessing the greenness of each step within the analytical procedure, providing a
406 comprehensive and detailed overview of the process. Multiple parameters were categorized as
407 green regarding reagents, solvents, compounds considering its health and safety hazard,
408 instrumentation, transport, yield, and conditions (see **Figure 3C**). Conversely, sample

409 collection and preservation, the necessity of an extraction step, and its scalability were rated
410 with a low degree of greenness (highlighted in red). The nature of solvents/reagents,
411 additional treatments, storage, and energy consumption were classified with a medium
412 environmental impact. Moreover, a value of $E = 0$ was obtained, indicating that no waste is
413 generated during the analytical process concerning the quantity of obtained products.
414 However, it is essential to consider that the Complex GAPI metrics consider a significantly
415 high number of restrictive parameters, the slight variation of which can significantly affect the
416 environmental impact. Specific considerations make some metrics genuinely challenging to
417 measure and assess.

418

419 To summarize, the sample preparation and method developed can be considered a promising
420 alternative to existing methods summarized in **Table 1S** (see Supplementary Material),
421 because it is an environmentally friendly method aligned with the GAC principles and the
422 first study supported by the AGREE, AGREEprep, and ComplexGAPI metrics (Gałuszka et
423 al., 2013; Shi et al., 2023), which demonstrated a consistent correlation among the metrics.

424

425 **3.4. Method validation**

426 The method validation was conducted in accordance with current legislation (EURACHEM
427 guide, 2014) and recent publications from our group (Fuente-Ballesteros et al., 2024).
428 Validation was carried out using blank samples, standards in the solvent, and matrix-matched
429 solutions obtained according to the selected sample treatment for honey samples (see
430 Subsections 2.3.2). Efficient chemometric statistical tools from Excel (Microsoft Office 2010,
431 Microsoft Corporation, Redmond, WA) were employed to process and analyze the data.

432

433 **3.4.1. Selectivity**

434 Selectivity was evaluated by comparing the chromatograms and mass spectra of standards in
435 solvents, standard in honey extracts and blank honeys of the three different botanical origins
436 ($n = 6$). As showed in **Figure 2** and **Figure 1S** (see Supplementary Material), no matrix
437 interferences were observed at analytes retention times. Moreover, similar mass spectra of the
438 analytes under study in solvent and standards in matrix extracts were obtained. The relative
439 intensities of the selected ions for each plasticizer in both types of standards were compared
440 and, for all cases, they were within $\pm 15\%$ of the relative intensity (data not shown), which is
441 within the established values $\pm 30\%$

442

443 **3.4.2. Limits of detection and quantification**

444 The limits of detection (LODs) and quantification (LOQs) were determined by the injection
445 of several blank samples measurement noise at the elution times for the studied plasticizers
446 and comparing this response (mean values) with the signal (peak heights) of compounds at
447 low concentration levels. The LODs and LOQs were estimated to be three and ten times the
448 S/N ratio, respectively. LODs values ranged from 0.2 to 2.1 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for thyme honeys, from
449 0.03 to 3.1 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for heather honeys, and from 0.04 to 0.5 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for rosemary honeys (see
450 **Table 1**). Meanwhile, LOQs values were comprised between 0.1 and 0.7 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for thyme
451 honeys, 0.1 and 10.3 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ to heather honeys, and 0.1 and 1.7 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for rosemary honeys
452 (see **Table 1**). All values for every matrix were below to the established SMLs (see **Table 1**)
453 (Official Journal of the European Union, 2011, 2023). They were comparable or better that
454 the reported values in literature and they were also much lower than the obtained in previous

455 works devoted to investigating these compounds in honeys (see Supplementary Material,
456 **Table 1S**).

457

458 **3.4.3. Matrix effect**

459 To ascertain how the matrix influenced the ionization for the analytes a comparison was made
460 of the detector responses (analyte peak area/IS area) of standard in solvent (R_{solvent}) and
461 standard in matrix extracts (R_{matrix} ; AF samples) of the different botanical origins spiked at
462 three different concentrations (QC levels). It was calculated as recommended in **X** using the
463 following formula Matrix effect (%) = $[(R_{\text{matrix}}/R_{\text{solvent}}) - 1] \times 100$. Analyte responses at the
464 three levels assayed in each matrix ranged in all cases between **-X**% of signal suppression to
465 **+X**% or signal enhancement (see **Table 3**). In addition, the slope confidence intervals (SCIs)
466 with standards in solvent and standards in matrix extracts were also compared, and it was not
467 found an overlapping of the SCI (see Supplementary Material, **Table 5S**). Therefore, the use
468 of calibration standards in solvent only would lead to an overestimate of the analyte
469 concentrations in the analyzed samples, and matrix matching for calibration is necessary for
470 background co-extractive abatement. Although the addition of a cleaning step with florisil in
471 the sample treatment significantly reduced the matrix effect (see Supplementary Material,
472 **Figure 1SD**), it could not be completely eliminated.

473

474 **3.4.4. Linearity/Working range**

475 Calibration curves ($n = 6$) were constructed by plotting the signal on the y-axis (analyte peak
476 area/IS area) against the analyte concentration on the x-axis. Linearity was evaluated by
477 visual analysis of the plots, a calculation being made of the determination coefficient (R^2),

478 and by our back calculation of the concentrations of the individual calibration standards. The
479 concentration of the analytical curves varied between LOQ and 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$ (LOQ, 50, 100,
480 250, 500, and 1000 $\mu\text{g L}^{-1}$), which corresponds to concentrations between LOQ and 2000 μg
481 kg^{-1} . The graphs obtained in all the calibration curves were straight lines, with R^2 values
482 higher than 0.99 in all cases (see Supplementary Material, **Table 5S**). Moreover, the deviation
483 of back-calculation concentration from true concentration was lower than 15% (data not
484 shown).

485

486 **3.4.5. Precision**

487 Precision was expressed as relative standard deviation (%RSD) and performed concurrently
488 by repeated sample analysis using BF samples, at three different concentrations levels (see
489 **Table 1**). These took place either on the same day (intra-day precision, repeatability,
490 EURACHEM guide, 2014), or over three consecutive days (inter-day precision, partial
491 reproducibility, EURACHEM guide, 2014). %RSD values were lower than 8% in all cases
492 (see Supplementary Material, **Table 6S**), which is consistent with the current European
493 legislation.

494

495 **3.4.6. Trueness**

496 Trueness was evaluated by means of recovery experiments (as a measure of trueness), by
497 comparing the results (analyte peak area/IS area) obtained from blank honey samples spiked
498 at three different concentrations (low, medium, and high QC levels; see **Table 1**), either prior
499 to (BF samples) or following (AF samples) sample treatment. Mean recoveries for the studied
500 plasticizers ranged from **X**% to **X**%, while %RSD values were lower than 6% in all cases (see
501 **Table 3**). Those values met the requirements stipulated by the European legislation (recovery

502 percentages between 70% and 120%; RSD \leq 20%) (ref) and are similar or better than the
503 recoveries obtained in previous works (see Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**).

504

505

506 **3.5. Application of the method**

507 The validated method was applied for the study of 6 PAEs, 1 adipate and 2 HDEs in different
508 honey samples. As described before, all of these were analyzed in triplicate, and the IS was
509 added at the same concentration in the samples. Honeys were handle based on the sample
510 procedures outlined in subsection 2.3.2. A total of n = 30 honey samples was analyzed and
511 categorized into two groups based on their origin: n = 14 honeys from experimental apiaries
512 (EA1-EA14) and n = 16 honeys obtained from local supermarkets (LS1-LS16). In all
513 samples, five analytes were detected (100% DEP, 80% DBP, 100% BBP, 93% DEHA, and
514 100% DEHP; data not shown), but only three of them were quantified (30% DEP, 100% BBP,
515 and 70% DEHA; see **Table 4**). The most contaminated samples were EA2, EA5, EA10, LS5,
516 LS7, LS10, and LS13 as they simultaneously contained DEP, BBP, and DEHA within a total
517 range concentration of 716 (LS7)-1410 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ (LS10). It should be noted that all of these
518 concentrations were below the established SMLs (Official Journal of the European Union,
519 2011, 2023) as other authors reported (Notardonato et al., 2020b). Thus, analyzed honeys can
520 be considered safe for human consumption. Nevertheless, this does not indicate a limitation in
521 the method's applicability since international organizations such as the European Commission
522 have already defined SMLs for these compounds in food products.

523

524 The occurrence of plasticizer residues, specifically PAEs and adipates, in honey is not a new
525 concern, as various cases of contamination have been documented in the literature previously
526 (see Supplementary Material, **Table 1S**). For instance, plasticizer concentrations in honeys

527 higher than 3000 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ were detected (Notardonato et al., 2020b) and DBP concentrations
528 levels 1.5-3 times higher than the SML were reported in Moroccan honeys (Massous et al.,
529 2023). In consonance with that two primary contamination pathways have been proposed.
530 Firstly, the presence of plasticizers in honey may originate from contaminated pollen and
531 nectar (Massous et al., 2023; Notardonato et al., 2020b). Indeed, these contaminants could
532 arise from environmental pollution (air, water, and/or soil) (Di Fiore et al., 2023; Lo Turco et
533 al., 2016), potentially due to the proximity of beehives to a large urban/industrial area
534 (Notardonato et al., 2020a). Secondly, production processes that involve direct contact with
535 unsuitable plastic cups (Koo et al., 2017), containers (Zhou et al., 2014), honeycombs
536 (Notardonato et al., 2020b), extractors, or uncappers (Lo Turco et al., 2016; Massous et al.,
537 2023) can contribute to contamination. The use of plastic honeycombs is increasingly
538 prevalent, primarily to safeguard the crop or prevent wax melting during the hottest periods of
539 the year (Notardonato et al., 2020b; Zhou et al., 2014). Additionally, crystallized honey is
540 typically heated to return it to a liquid state, which enhances the release of plasticizers
541 (Kartalovic et al., 2021; Zhou et al., 2014). Moreover, the acidity and high moisture content
542 of honey might influence the transfer of harmful organic additives from the plastic cup to the
543 honey, contributing to migration (Koo et al., 2017; Peñalver et al., 2021). Extended storage
544 under specific conditions of temperature, humidity, and light can not only impact the
545 distinctive physicochemical properties of honey, but also lead to gradual polymer
546 degradation. Consequently, this degradation can result in the migration of plastic additives
547 from the packaging into the honey (Massous et al., 2023). For instance, an increase in
548 phthalate concentration was observed when the honeys were exposed to thermal stresses,
549 indicating plastic release from the containers. It is hypothesized that high temperatures,
550 irradiation, and exposure to ultraviolet rays from the sun can degrade plastics (Notardonato et
551 al., 2020b). In different scenarios, some beekeepers in Malaysia placed rows of plastic cups

552 within wooden boxes to simulate the shape and arrangement of natural honey and pollen pots.
553 The objective was to provide pre-made storage pots to stimulate stingless bees to increase
554 their nectar foraging activity and subsequently boost honey production for commercial
555 purposes (Koo et al., 2017). From our perspective, despite the increasing use of plastic due to
556 its affordability, thermal sealing capabilities, optical properties, and versatility in
557 manufacturing various shapes and sizes, it is crucial to consider its biodegradability,
558 decomposition, and migration upon contact with food (Kartalovic et al., 2021).

559

560 Ultimately, the identification of contaminant residues associated with plastics in honey
561 underscores the importance of developing analytical methods to ensure the safety of these
562 products and preserve human health since some of them had been classified as endocrine
563 disruptors (Notardonato et al., 2020b; Zhou et al., 2014). While this situation has been widely
564 studied in different types of food, beverages and food stimulants, however, to the best of our
565 knowledge, there is a little information regarding honey samples. In studies, there should be
566 an increase in the number of samples analyzed (often less than 12) and the testing of honeys
567 from different geographical and botanical origins to attain a more comprehensive perspective.
568 Furthermore, in accordance with the EU Regulation, the limitation of $60 \times 10^3 \mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for
569 those compounds without a defined SML requires careful consideration. This elevated value
570 implies that the additive is allowed for use in polymer production for food packaging without
571 restrictions.

572

573 **3.6. Risk assessment**

574 To evaluate potential hazards associated with the honey samples under study, the average
575 concentration of each plasticizer was utilized in calculating the estimated daily intake (EDI)

576 following the formula: $EDI = CI \times IR / bw$ (Ekici et al., 2024; Isci & Dagdemir, 2024; Xie et al.,
577 2023). EDI expresses the plasticizer exposure per unit of body weight resulting from honey
578 consumption ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$), where CI represents the mean plasticizer concentration in honey
579 samples ($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$), and IR is the ingestion rate of honey set at 50 g/day for adults (Sadeghi et
580 al., 2020) with a corresponding reference body weight (bw) of 70 kg. The assessment of non-
581 carcinogenic health risks was conducted through the hazard quotient (HQ) for individual
582 plasticizers, calculated as follows: $HQ = EDI / RfD$. The reference dose (RfD) values for
583 DEP, BBP and DEHA were 8×10^{-2} , 2×10^{-1} , 6×10^{-2} mg/kg bw/day, respectively (ECHA,
584 2012; EPA, 2004). The hazard index (HI) was determined as the total sum of individual HQ
585 contributions ($HI = \sum HQ \text{ DEP} + HQ \text{ BBP} + HQ \text{ DEHA}$) (U.S. EPA, 2019). HQ and HI
586 values below 1 imply no significant non-carcinogenic risks to human health.

587

588 This study evaluated, for the first time, the potential non-carcinogenic health risk associated
589 with plasticizer consumption in honey samples sourced from various botanical origins using,
590 employing parameters such as EDI, HQ and HI (see Supplementary Material, **Table 7S**). The
591 average EDI values for DEP, BBP and DEHA ranged from 0.3-1.0 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$,
592 significantly lower than tolerable daily intake values (TDI) of 50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$ for DEP and
593 BBP, and 300 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$ for DEHA (Nehring et al., 2020; Silano et al., 2019; Weiss et al.,
594 2018). BBP exhibited the highest EDI values for all samples, peaking at 0.521 $\mu\text{g}/\text{kg bw}/\text{day}$.
595 The assessment of HQ and HI (see Supplementary Material, **Figure 3S** and **Table 7S**)
596 revealed these values to be at least 100 times lower than the threshold value of 1, as reported
597 by the EPA (Año), suggesting a negligible non-carcinogenic health risk association.
598 Consequently, our results indicate a lack of apparent risk to consumer health. However, the
599 scarcity of existing literature concerning direct comparisons between honey consumption and

600 plasticizer exposure underscores the necessity for further research in this area. These
601 circumstances highlight the urgency for continued investigation in this field.

602

603 **4. Conclusions**

604 In this study, an analytical methodology has been developed and optimized to determine 6
605 PAEs, 1 adipate, and 2 HDEs in honey samples using GC-MS. We proposed an efficient,
606 simple, and environmentally compatible sample treatment involving a double solvent
607 extraction with ethyl acetate followed by a purification step with florisil. To the best of our
608 knowledge, this is the first instance of developing a sample method for a mixture of
609 plasticizers, including ethers, in honey samples. This procedure not only allowed for
610 achieving good recovery rates but also minimized the matrix effect in all cases, a situation not
611 commonly encountered when analyzing these bee products. Additionally, a greenness
612 assessment was conducted, resulting in the formulation of an environmentally friendly
613 method. This evaluation is novel as the consideration of green methodologies has not been
614 previously integrated into the study of plasticizers in honey. The method was validated
615 according to current legislation, and the results demonstrated that the analytical performance
616 of the method was similar or superior in many cases compared to previous studies. The LOD
617 and LOQ values obtained were lower than the SMLs established for the studied compounds
618 and comparable to the best published values. Finally, the proposed and validated method was
619 applied to analyze several honey samples from different origins and regions obtained from
620 apiaries and local markets. Residues of plasticizers (DEP, BBP, and DEHA) were detected in
621 certain honey, but no concentrations above the established SMLs were found. Finally, an
622 assessment of the risk revealed that the analyzed honey samples do not pose an apparent risk
623 to human health.

624

625 **Abbreviations**

626 **4-BDE**, 4-bromodiphenyl ether; **4-CDE**, 4-chlorodiphenyl ether; **AF**, samples spiked after
627 sample treatment; **AGREE**, analytical greenness calculator; **BBP**, benzyl butyl phthalate; **BF**,
628 samples spiked before sample treatment; **bw**, body weight; **CI**, mean plasticizer concentration
629 in honey samples; **DBP**, dibutyl phthalate; **DBP-d₄**, dibutyl phthalate-3,4,5,6-d₄; **DEHA**,
630 bis(2-ethylhexyl)adipate; **DEHP**, bis(2-ethylhexyl)phthalate; **DEP**, diethyl phthalate;
631 **DLLME**, dispersive liquid-liquid microextraction; **DMP**, dimethyl phthalate; **DNOP**, di-n-
632 octyl phthalate; **EDI**, estimated the daily intake; **EI**, electronic impact; **EtOAc**, ethyl acetate;
633 **GAC**, green analytical principles; **GAPI**, green analytical procedure index; **GC**, gas
634 chromatography; **GC-MS**, gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry; **HDEs**,
635 halodiphenyl ethers; **HI**, hazard index; **HQ**, hazard quotient; **IL**, ionic liquids; **IR**, ingestion
636 rate; **IS**, internal standard; **LC**, liquid chromatography; **LOD**, limit of detection; **LOQ**, limit
637 of quantification; **m/z**, mass-to-charge; **MS**, mass spectrometry; **MS/MS**; tandem mass
638 spectrometry; **MSPE**, magnetic solid-phase extraction; **NADES**, natural deep eutectic
639 solvents; **PAEs**, phthalates; **PET**, polyethylene terephthalate; **PVC**, polyvinyl chloride; **QC**,
640 concentration levels; **R²**, determination coefficient; **RfD**, reference dose; **RSD**, relative
641 standard deviation; **S/N**, signal-to-noise; **SCI**, slope confidence intervals; **SE**, solvent
642 extraction; **SIM**, selected ion monitoring; **SMLs**, specific migration limits; **SPE**, solid phase
643 extraction; **TDI**, tolerable daily intake values; **TOF-MS**, time of flight-mass spectrometry;
644 **USAEME**; ultrasound-assisted emulsification microextraction;

645

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649

650 **Conflict of interest statement**

651 The authors of this manuscript declare no conflict of interest.

652

653 **Data availability**

654 The datasets generated during the current study are included in this published article, or they
655 are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

656

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948

949 **Figure captions**

950 **Figure 1.-** Analytical sample preparation work-up flow chart based on a double solvent
951 extraction to study plastic-related chemicals in honey samples.

952

953 **Figure 2.-** Representative GC-MS chromatograms (SIM mode using the quantification/target
954 ions; see **Table 1**) obtained from a standard in solvent mixture (1.0 mg L⁻¹; IS, 0.1 mg L⁻¹).
955 GC-MS conditions are summarized in Subsection 2.4 and **Tables 1** and **2**. **1**, dimethyl
956 phthalate (DMP); **2**, diethyl phthalate (DEP); **3**, 4-chlorodiphenyl ether (4-CDE); **4**, 4-
957 bromodiphenyl ether (4-BDE); **5**, dibutyl phthalate (DBP); **6**, dibutyl phthalate-3,4,5,6-d4
958 (DBP-d4); **7**, benzyl butyl phthalate (BBP); **8**, bis(2-ethylhexyl)adipate (DEHA); **9**, bis(2-
959 ethylhexyl)phthalate (DEHP); **10**, di-n-octyl phthalate (DNOP).

960

961 **Figure 3.-** Greenness evaluation using A) AGREE, B) AGREEprep, and C) Complex GAPI
962 metrics.

963